

CO₂-SPICER - CO₂ Storage Pilot In a CarbonatE Reservoir

R5.5 Report and dataset: Laboratory experiments on water- CO₂-rock interactions, dissolution, precipitation, geochemical cementation modelling

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1 INTRODUCTION

Several publications on carbon capture and storage (CCS) mention and detail specific experiments that precede the implementation of CCS in various geological structures (Gaus 2010; Yasuhara et al. 2004; Zhang et al. 2019; Ayayi et al. 2019; Foroutan et al. 2021; Wang et al. 2019). Experiments with mixed fluids between supercritical CO₂ and saline NaCl have been described (Kaszuba et al. 2005; Labus and Bujok 2011; Gau et al. 2008). Experiments have shown that the injection of CO₂ into the rock system leads to complex and significant changes in the nature of such a system. One of many accompanying phenomena is, for example, the nucleation and growth of new carbonate and silicate minerals (Gaus et al. 2008; Zhou et al. 2014; Marty et al. 2009). The accompanying phenomenon is a change in the permeability of the storage reservoir structure, which may have a negative impact on the entire storage system. The same has been demonstrated in experiments simulating P-T conditions of real potential storage. It turns out that the interaction between the CO₂-H₂O system of sedimentary rock with carbonate cement leads to the dissolution and re-formation of carbonate minerals (Radvanec et al. 2008; Wertz et al. 2014). The study of Brandl et al. also mentions the reduction of porosity near injection boreholes. Clogging involves reactions between carbonates, clay and related minerals, oxides, hydroxides, and iron sulfides. A significant, and in some cases essential, source component for the formation of clogging minerals is the borehole's own material, the grouting (Bujok et al. 2014; Wertz et al. 2013). Crystallization processes are controlled mainly by the partial pressure of CO₂, pH, and groundwater flow (Fetter 2001; Appelo and Postma 2005). Oxidation-reduction reactions of iron are also of major importance.

Processes occurring in the environment of the reservoir after CO₂ injections have been clearly and conclusively described in many articles (Zhang et al. 2019; Ayayi et al. 2019; Foroutan et al. 2021; Wang et al. 2019), particularly those relating to geochemical changes in both the reservoir and the overlying confining layer (Gaus 2010; Yasuhara et al. 2004; Ayayi et al. 2019). Changes in minerals and pore space can affect storage capacity and injectivity in the short term; in the long run, they affect the distribution of individual phases (fluids, rocks) Zhang et al. 2019; Wertz et al. 2014). Therefore, it is necessary to model the various aspects of these processes, both at the microscale (e.g., changes in minerals and pore space) and at the macroscale (e.g., the development of new preferential migration pathways due to the dissolution of minerals, fluid quality changes, etc.). Geochemical modelling of rock alterations is therefore a key supportive method for assessing the safe operation of future storage (Wang et al. 2019). This study is focused on simulating chemical processes in CO₂-rock-brackish water systems in a pilot research environment of CO₂ storage in the Žarošice area (Zar-3, South Moravia, Czech Republic). This location is an extracted oil deposit and is potentially suitable for CO₂ injection.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

Models involving kinetic transport through porous media and thermodynamic issues of multiphase systems are very useful in forecasting the impact of CO₂ injections on the changes to the rock environment at the site. These models are based on information regarding petrophysical, mineralogical, and hydrogeological characteristics of porous media, hydrochemical analysis of fluid composition, pressure and temperature values of the deposit, and kinetic parameters.

2.1 Samples: geological setting and petrography

The area of interest, representing the surroundings of the structure referred to as “Zar-3” (Žarošice hydrocarbon field), is located in the southeastern part of the Czech Republic. The wider area of interest encompasses 94.5 km². Wider surroundings of the Žarošice oil and gas field covers the contact zone between the west European foreland plate (West European Platform) and the Western Carpathian thrust belt in the territory of southern Moravia (southeastern part of the Czech Republic). The European foreland plate in southern Moravia is represented by the Bohemian Massif, which consists of the Hercynian orogenic system of Western Europe and its late Precambrian (Cadomian) foreland terrain called the Brunovistulicum that extends far below the Carpathian belt. The Early Paleozoic sedimentation started with Cambrian clastics. In the Ordovician and Silurian period (Caledonian) hiatus is assumed.

Since the Middle Devonian, the Brunovistulicum passed through two full plate-tectonic cycles, the Hercynian and the Tethyan–Alpine cycles (Picha, 1996). The Paleozoic Hercynian cycle in the area began with rifting and deposition of the late Early to Middle Devonian clastics. In the Late Devonian to Early Carboniferous, carbonate platforms and basins evolved on passive continental margins. At the onset of the Hercynian orogeny in the Early Carboniferous, the carbonate sedimentation was replaced by synorogenic flysch (Culm) facies, which, in the Late Carboniferous, was followed by the late orogenic and postorogenic molasse with coal beds (Kostelnicek et al., 2006).

The Mesozoic to Cenozoic Alpine cycle in southern Moravia began with continental rifting in the Early Jurassic and deposition of synrift detrital deposits, followed by marine transgression and deposition of mixed carbonate and siliciclastic rocks of the passive margins. The carbonate platforms occupied the shallow marginal zone and uplifted rift blocks, whereas the organic rich marly facies (Mikulov marls) formed in a deeper basinal environment.

During the Late Cretaceous to early Paleogene, the European foreland in Moravia was uplifted and deeply eroded. Rivers cut the deep Nesvačilka and Vranovice valleys that turned into submarine canyons more than 1500 m deep, which were gradually filled with the Paleogene detrital organic-rich deposits (Picha, 1979, 1996; Jiricek, 1987).

In the early Late Cretaceous, the Carpathian passive margins were converted into a foreland-type synorogenic basin marked by deep-water turbiditic flysch sedimentation, followed by a late orogenic and postorogenic shallow-marine and continental molasse sedimentation. During the late phases of the Alpine orogeny, in the late Paleogene and early Miocene, the flysch sequences were deformed and thrust over the European foreland, including the inner zone of the Neogene foredeep (Kostelnicek et al., 2006). The Carpathian thrust belt in Moravia is composed of Late Jurassic to early Miocene synorogenic sequences of the flysch belt (Fig. 2-1). The Neogene foredeep, with the exception of the innermost zones adjacent to the front of the thrust belt, remained undeformed. Superimposed on the thrust belt is the Neogene Vienna Basin.

The most promising exploration targets proved to be the basal sandstones and the carbonates of Jurassic, occurring as isolated erosional relicts on the northern slope of the Nesvačilka graben. These relicts (buried hills) are sealed mainly by impermeable shales and mudstones of the paleo valley fill. The isolated bodies of turbiditic and channelized sandstones enclosed within the Paleogene fill of the Nesvačilka paleo valley represent the secondary exploration play.

Geochemical studies (Francu et al., 1996; Krejci et al., 1996; Picha and Peters, 1998) suggest that the hydrocarbons in the Nesvačilka graben area were predominantly sourced from Jurassic, organic-rich Mikulov marls. The Paleogene shales and mudstones may be considered as additional source rocks, especially for gas.

Žarošice field is a buried Jurassic patch reef, which was subsequently dolomitized and faulted and partially eroded from the west (Fig. 2-1). The seal is provided by two different cap rocks, Jurassic Mikulov Marl in the eastern part of the field and Paleogene claystone I the western and northern part. The reservoir rock is mainly heavily fractured Vranovice Dolomite and in the southern part near the base by dolomitic sandstones of the Nikolčice beds (Fig. 2-1). Primary porosity of the dolomite is around 1 – 3 %. Much more important is the secondary porosity which is based on log data reaching 2 – 9 % (locally even more). Permeability of the reservoirs was estimated (based on hydrodynamic tests; Durica et al., 2010) 193 – 630 mD.

Žarošice field was discovered by ZA3 well in depth 1565 – 1872 m, it is an oil field with a gas cap and active aquifer. The gas cap reaches thicknesses up to 150 m, the original oil zone was approximately 105 m thick. GOC and OWC were estimated based on log data and are periodically updated during production (observation well ZA 3).

The oil is medium heavy reaching 0.908 g·cm⁻³ at 20°C (24,4°API). It is of paraffin/naphthene type with low benzene content. Viscosity of the (dead) oil at 20°C is 40 mPa·s. The gas cap is mainly methane (92 %) with 4.8 % other hydrocarbon gases and 3.2 % nitrogen and CO₂. Solution gas content about 83 % methane and 7.5 % CO₂. The original static reservoir pressure (on GOC) was 17,172 MPa, temperature 51.4°C. Original viscosity at reservoir condition was 3.67 cp, Original FVF was 1.183 m³/m and Rs 63.7 m³/m. 8 production wells were drilled, 4 of them horizontal from both sides of the field. About horizontal wells 1 is abandoned due to 100 % WCUT. Cumulative production is 460 mcm of oil and 46 mcm of gas. Žarošice field is nearing the end of production.

Fig. 2-1: Zar-3 site – NNW-SSE geological profile with well logs (depth below sea level) (Opletal et al., 2022).

2.2 Experimental setup

Data and outputs, from laboratory experiments carried out in the laboratories of the Department of Geological Engineering at VSB – Technical University of Ostrava and data received from partners within the project, were used for modelling. These were mainly mineralogical, petrographic, geochemical, and hydrogeological characteristics of reservoir and cap rocks and the composition of brine as a reaction solution.

2.2.1 Input data

The following data were used for numerical models of geochemical processes at the studied location:

1. the existence of supercritical CO₂ in the structure (spCO₂ = 150 bar) and a temperature of 53°C;
2. samples of rock material of the reservoir, overlying and underlying cap rocks at the Zar-3 location;
3. the chemical composition of the water phase, which simulates the composition of the pore water in the reservoir.

Ad 2) A model of reservoir rocks of the Vranovice dolomite formation (labelled ZA4A) from the locality of Zar-3 was considered. A description of the rock is given in Table 2-1. The Vranovice formation lies at a depth of about 1500 m and is formed by an Upper Jurassic dolomite about 100.0 million years old. Used ZA4A samples are considered representative samples of the rock of the storage reservoir. It is a light grey dolomite by lithology, from what is called the Vranovice formation.

Tab. 2-1: The samples of reservoir rocks

Borehole	Core	Box	True vertical depth (m)	Stratigraphy	Lithostratigraphy	Lithology
ZA4A	3	3	1528.5 – 1537.5	Upper Jurassic	Vranovice fm.	light gray dolomite
ZA4A	4	2	1571.0 – 1578.8	Upper Jurassic	Vranovice fm.	light gray dolomite

For models of seal rocks were used rock sample of the Žarošice Mb. (labelled ZA4 1/5) from the locality of Zar-3 and rock sample of the Myslejovice formation (labelled UH16 6/1) from locality Uhřice. A description of the rocks is given in Table 2. The Myslejovice formation lies at a depth of about 2000 m and is created by Lower Carbonaceous turbidites, alternating dark shales/ siltstones (1-3 mm) and sandstones (5 - 20 cm) about 350.0 million years old. The Žarošice Mb. is stored in a depth of about 1500 m and is formed by Middle Paleogene dark gray shaly siltstone.

Tab. 2-2: The samples of seal rocks

Borehole	Core	Box	True vertical depth (m)	Stratigraphy	Lithostratigraphy	Lithology
ZA4	1	5	1569.0 – 1577.0	Middle Paleogene	Žarošice Mb.	dark gray shaly siltstone
UH16	6	1	2077.0 – 2083.5	Lower Carbon	Myslejovice fm.	dark shales/siltstones, sandstones

Ad 3) As a sample of the water phase, which forms the filling of the pore space of the reservoir formation in the so-called Vranovice formation, the water solution from a well ZA4A was used. The water sample from the aquifer was taken by the project partner (MND) from a depth of 1530 meters and the chemical analysis of the water was carried out in the laboratories of the VSB – Technical University of Ostrava. The chemical composition of this solution is shown in Tab. 2-3.

Tab. 2-3: Physico-chemical parameters of brackish water from a well Žarošice

Brackish water Žarošice 4A		
Ca ²⁺	(mg/l)	111.0
Mg ²⁺	(mg/l)	107.0
Na ⁺	(mg/l)	8570.0
K ⁺	(mg/l)	252.0
Cl ⁻	(mg/l)	12300.0
NH ₄ ⁺	(mg/l)	32.6
Br ⁻	(mg/l)	54.0
I ⁻	(mg/l)	43.0
HCO ₃ ⁻	(mg/l)	2580.0
SO ₄ ²⁻	(mg/l)	535.0
Li	(mg/l)	3.2
Sr	(mg/l)	19.2
Mn	(mg/l)	0.0
Fe	(mg/l)	0.4
B	(mg/l)	43.0
TDS	(mg/l)	24590.0
Other parameters		
T	(°C)	53
pH	-	7.1
depth	meter	1530

2.2.2 Mineralogical and petrophysical properties of the studied rock samples

The mineralogical and petrophysical properties of the studied rock samples at the location in question are described in Tab. 2-4.

Tab. 2-4: Mineralogical composition of the studied rock sample (wt%) and conversion to percentages by volume (vol. %)

Well	Dol	Dol Ca-Fe	Q	Calc	Mu	Ka	Mic	Alb	Chl	Pyr	Porosity	Specific surface
ZA4A	(wt%)	(wt%)	(wt%)	(wt%)	(wt%)	(wt%)	(wt%)	(wt%)	(wt%)	(wt%)	(%)	(m ² /g)
	55.04	17.95	4.01	0.00	2.88	3.12	7.66	7.92	1.42	0.00	-	1.054
	(vol. %)	(vol. %)	(vol. %)	(vol. %)	(vol. %)	(vol. %)	(vol. %)	(vol. %)	(vol. %)	(vol. %)	(%)	
ZA4	(wt%)	(wt%)	(wt%)	(wt%)	(wt%)	(wt%)	(wt%)	(wt%)	(wt%)	(wt%)	(%)	(m ² /g)
	-	18,10	57,10	0,30	4,00	-	16,68	1,18	1,14	1,50	-	0.886
	(vol. %)	(vol. %)	(vol. %)	(vol. %)	(vol. %)	(vol. %)	(vol. %)	(vol. %)	(vol. %)	(vol. %)	(%)	
UH16	(wt%)	(wt%)	(wt%)	(wt%)	(wt%)	(wt%)	(wt%)	(wt%)	(wt%)	(wt%)	(%)	(m ² /g)
	-	-	51,32	1,65	3,58	-	17,52	18,4	7,53	-	-	1.154
	(vol. %)	(vol. %)	(vol. %)	(vol. %)	(vol. %)	(vol. %)	(vol. %)	(vol. %)	(vol. %)	(vol. %)	(%)	
	-	-	50,51	1,62	3,52	-	17,24	18,11	7,41	-	1.57	

* Q—quartz, Mu—muscovite, Mi—microcline, Ka—kaolinite, Chl—chlorite, Calc—calcite, Dol—dolomite, Alb—albite, Pyr -Pyrite.

The mineralogical composition of all rock samples was determined by XRD analysis. XRD powder data were measured at room temperature on a Bruker AXS D8 θ - θ powder diffractometer in Bragg-Brentan parafocusing geometry using CoK α wavelength ($\lambda = 1.7903 \text{ \AA}$, $U = 34 \text{ kV}$, $I = 30 \text{ mA}$). Porosity of reservoir rock was determined by the project partner (MND) with using by geophysics in well data from acoustic logging; Hg-porosimetry was used in the case of seal rock samples. The specific surface area was found by the N₂-BET method by adsorption-desorption isotherms. The samples from borehole ZA4A, ZA4 and UH16 were analysed before the experiments in reaction chamber and after the experimental intervals.

2.2.3 Hydrogeological parameters of the Vranovice formation

The hydrogeological parameters of the reservoir at the location are described in Tab. 2-5.

Tab. 2-5: Hydrogeological parameters of reservoir rock – light grey dolomite

Parameters	Value	Unit
thickness	200	m
porosity	8.00	%
horizontal permeability k_R	500	mD
vertical permeability k_z	1600	mD
pressure P	150	bar
temperature T	53	°C
max. salinity S	72	g/l
CO ₂ density	195	kg/m ³
CO ₂ viscosity	1.5E-4	Pa.s

The hydrogeological parameters of the Vranovice formation are important for understanding and predicting changes in the storage area. It is assumed there is higher horizontal permeability k_R than vertical permeability k_z due to the geological processes undergone during sedimentation. These data were taken from the project partner (MND).

The density and viscosity of CO₂ are dynamically determined in the TOUGHREACT program by the ECO2N module as a function of pressure P, temperature T and salinity S (Pruess, 2005; Pruess et al., 1999).

2.2.4 Experiments in react chamber

The sample material (rock type and representative sample size), geological environment (pressure, temperature, and salinity) and operating conditions were considered for setting up the experimental equipment. CO₂ injection was performed using a reactor with a closed hyperbaric chamber, where dry CO₂ was pumped at pressures of 150 bar and temperatures of 53 °C. These conditions represent the host geological environment. The exposure time of the rock sample to CO₂ varied from 30 to 180 days.

The reaction chamber is a cylindrical vessel with an outer diameter of 169 mm and a length of 955 mm, welded from a shell made of stainless steel and DN150 PN160 flanges. The lids (blind flanges DN150 PN160) are also made of stainless steel. The apparatus is divided into two parts, in which there are two reaction cells. The inner diameter of the reaction cells is 141 mm, the length of the cells is 368 mm. The inside of the cells is provided with a protective coating and the cells are further lined. The lining is inert to CO₂. On the side of the casing, two pins are welded for placing the pressure vessel in the bearings enabling its positioning and rocking movement ensured by the rocking mechanism.

The highest operating pressure is 200 bar. The range of operating temperatures is 5°-80°C. The heating of the reaction chamber is ensured by means of a temperature spiral. The operating medium can be reservoir water, hydrocarbons, CO₂, nitrogen. The dynamic conditions of the geohydrodynamic system are simulated by changing the position of the reaction chamber with two swings per day (the setting was used when solving the issue of CO₂ geosequestration). Changes in position are secured using a swinging mechanism driven by an electric motor.

The advantage of this lab device is that long-term measurements of physical processes and chemical reactions occurring between the fluid filling and the investigated macro-samples (rocks) can be carried out on a structurally simple device under pressure and temperature conditions corresponding to in situ conditions, namely under dynamic system conditions.

Two experiments in reaction chamber were realized. The conditions used in the reaction chamber were 53°C and 150 bar like experimental temperature and pressure. The experiments took place for 30, 90, 120 and 180 days. The brackish water of known composition (see Tab. 2-3) from the well ZA4A was used as the reaction solution.

First experiment with reservoir rock samples started at January 2022. The collector rock samples came from the borehole ZA4A (core 3/ box 3). We worked with samples of seal rocks in the second experiment. This experiment has begun in November 2022. The samples of tasted rocks came from boreholes ZA4 (core 1/ box 5), respectively UH16 (core 6/ box 1). The lithology and mineralogical composition of the samples before experiment are described in Tabs. 2-1, 2-2 and 2-4.

2.3 Geochemical modelling

The results presented in the following chapter are the outputs of equilibrium and kinetic modelling of the geochemical reactivity of the CO₂-water-rock system, determining the influence of CO₂ on the porosity.

Equilibrium models were designed to evaluate changes in porous water chemistry after CO₂ injection into the reservoir to express balances in the rock-CO₂-brackish water system, and to express the solubility of CO₂ in brackish water ZA4A well. Kinetic modelling was conducted to evaluate hydrogeochemical changes in the studied formation in relation to the injection and storage of CO₂ in the structure. This allowed for the assessment of volumes and quantities of precipitated or dissolved mineral phases and of their impact on reservoir rock permeability in relation to the prediction of possible CO₂-related risks.

The Geochemist's Workbench modelling program was used to meet the above objectives. Kinetic and thermodynamic models were applied using The Geochemist's Workbench (GWB) Release 6.0 (Bethke 2006).

3 RESULTS

Immediately after injection, CO₂ diffuses in its supercritical form and partially dissolves into the groundwater. This process significantly changes the mineralogical, hydrogeological and geochemical conditions in the deposit. It acidifies the original brackish groundwater, it can affect changes in hydrogeological parameters, especially the porosity and permeability of the storage rock, it changes the mineralogical composition of the rock of the storage area, it can also affect the mineralogical changes of the sealing layers in the overburden, it causes chemical changes in the cement equipment of the wells. All these reactions can be a potential risk in the CO₂ storage process in the selected structure and can lead to CO₂ leakage from the storage to the surface. It is therefore necessary to understand the mechanism of these reactions, quantify them and evaluate them to ensure the safety and sustainability of storage.

3.1 Model changes in brackish water chemistry after CO₂ injection

The reaction of CO₂ with groundwater and its effects on potential storage are of utmost importance for the process of mineral sequestration because only a dissolved form of CO₂ can react with the rock. CO₂ solubility is a function of the temperature, pressure, and salinity of the solution, with CO₂ solubility decreasing with increases in the temperature and molarity of the solution, while CO₂ solubility increases with increasing pressure. The dissolution was carried out until the thermodynamic equilibrium was reached and the solution was saturated with CO₂. Based on the input parameters used in the PHREEQC model (brackish water ZA4A chemistry, PCO₂ = 150 bar, and temperature = 53°C), we report the theoretical acidification of brackish water ZA4A as a result of CO₂ injection and calculated chemistry changes in Tab. 3-1. The HCO₃⁻ ion is the dominant carbonate component in the solution at alkaline pH. When the pH drops to the acidic values, the bicarbonate ions decrease in solution and carbonic acid, respectively, and CO₂(aq)

(Appelo and Postma 2005; Stumm and Morgan 1995) becomes the dominant carbonate component.

Tab. 3-1: Original and model-calculated acidification of brackish water from a ZA4A well

		Original brackish water Žarošice 4A	Acidified Žarošice 4A from model
Ca ²⁺	(mg/l)	111.0	111.58
Mg ²⁺	(mg/l)	107.0	108.03
Na ⁺	(mg/l)	8570.0	8565.23
K ⁺	(mg/l)	252.0	257.45
Cl ⁻	(mg/l)	12300.0	12314.67
NH ₄ ⁺	(mg/l)	32.6	32.64
Br ⁻	(mg/l)	54.0	54.15
I ⁻	(mg/l)	43.0	42.76
<hr/>			
HCO ₃ ⁻ /CO _{2(aq)}	(mg/l)	2580.0	115,846.24
SO ₄ ²⁻	(mg/l)	535.0	528.89
Li	(mg/l)	3.2	3.24
Sr	(mg/l)	19.2	18.91
Mn	(mg/l)	0.0	1.45
Fe	(mg/l)	0.4	0.28
B	(mg/l)	43.0	41.20
TDS	(mg/l)	24590.0	24590.29
<hr/>			
Other parameters			
T	(°C)	53	53
pH	-	7.1	4.2
depth	meter	1530	

* TDS—total dissolved substances; T—temperature; log P_{CO₂} = 2.065.

The calculations in program Phreeqc Interactive 3.7.3. were carried out to confirm the changes in the chemistry of the input water after CO₂ injection.

The dissolution of CO₂ in the solution results in a decrease in pH and an enrichment of carbonate ions according to the following reactions:

After the reaction of brackish water Žarošice 4A with spCO₂, there was an increase in CO_{2(aq)} to a value of 115846.24 mg/L as a result of the dissolution of CO_{2(g)} according to equation (1) under the given conditions P_{CO₂} = 150 bar and temperature 53°C. This process had the effect of acidifying the brackish water, i.e. lowering the pH to a value of 4.2. This is also related to other changes in the chemistry of the acidified brine compared to the original composition.

We observe a slight decrease in the concentration of sodium and sulphate ions, on the contrary, the concentration of chlorides increased slightly. During the reaction of brackish

water with spCO₂, Na⁺ cations reacted with sulphates and bicarbonates to form NaSO₄⁻ and NaHCO₃ complexes.

The most important changes when CO₂ was pushed into the pore environment of the collector saturated with brackish water were the carbonate substances in the solution. The concentration of bicarbonates, which participated in the buffering of the system during CO₂ injection, dropped significantly, which is one of the most important properties of the carbonate system. The buffering capacity of the system is expressed by the buffering intensity. This indicates the equivalent amount of H⁺ protons or OH⁻ ions needed to change the pH by one unit. The carbonate system responds to a change in pH by (a) increasing the concentration of OH⁻ ions by protolyzes of H₂CO₃^{*}, releasing H⁺ ions into solution and forming HCO₃⁻ ions, and (b) accepting H⁺ ions by HCO₃⁻ ions and forming H₂CO₃^{*} (Stumm and Morgan, 1995). These processes are shown in Fig. 3-1.

Fig. 3-1: Graphic presentation of the equivalence points of carbonate species in solution derived from the proton balance of the species (modified from Stumm and Morgan, 1995).

The process of dissolving CO₂ in a brackish water solution result in the dissolution of certain minerals of the geological environment in which the CO₂ is injected and then is followed by the precipitation of new minerals. This can ultimately lead to changes in the permeability of the rock environment and to a reduction in the capacity of the injected CO₂.

3.2 Evolution of the reservoir and cap rocks during and after CO₂ injection – the geochemical modelling

Models of pH and porosity development during and after CO₂ injection were implemented in the GWB program. The input parameters were the porosity data of samples ZA4A 8%, ZA4 0.886% and UH16 1.154%, the specific resistance of the brine in the collector is 5Ωm, the fugacity $f_{\text{CO}_2} = 70$ bars, the original pH of the brine 7.1 and the temperature 53°C, the chemical composition of the brine from Tab. 2-3 and the mineral composition of the collector and cap rocks from Tab. 2-4.

The models were created in the first step for the acidification of the original solution at the desired CO₂ pressure ($f_{\text{CO}_2} = 70$ bar), then for the first six months of CO₂ injection into the structure and the last model for the degassing processes in reservoir and cap rocks.

The models are valid for a homogeneous pore medium with 100% saturation of the pore with brine solution at a constant injected amount and pT conditions in the repository. The injected amount of CO₂ is assumed to be 8750 tCO₂/year, which corresponds to an injection rate of 0.28 kgCO₂/s.

3.2.1 First model step – acidification of original solution

1) Reservoir rock

Fig. 3-2: Development of pH and porosity in solution with reservoir rock during acidification of original brackish water solution.

During the injection of CO₂ into the collector of the potential storage, there will be a quick drop in pH in the solution of the original brackish water from the original pH value of 7.1 to the pH value of 5.7 (Fig. 3-2 left). The subsequent gradual decline is controlled by the carbonate dissolution reaction. After about 18 hours, the pH stabilizes at a value of 4.7.

The porosity of the collector decreases during CO₂ injection from the original 8% to a value of 6.9% after 24 hours (Fig. 3-2 right). Reduced porosity is related to rapid dissolution of dolomite (Fig. 3-3A) and precipitation of secondary minerals, mainly gypsum (Fig. 3-3B) and calcite (Fig. 3-3A).

Fig. 3-3: Development of (A) carbonate and (B) sulphate minerals saturation in acidification brackish water during the CO₂ injection.

II) Paleogene and Carbon cap rock

During the interaction of acidification and supersaturated to CO₂ brackish water with over- and underlying cap rocks, there will be a decrease in pH in the solution from the original pH value of 7.1 to the pH value of 4.9 (Figs. 3-4 and 3-5 left).

pH is some lower than in original water because of achieving the hydrochemical balance between the species in solution.

Fig. 3-4: Development of pH and porosity in solution with Paleogene cap rock during acidification of original brackish water solution.

The porosity of the Paleogene cap rock increases during CO₂ injection from the original 0.886% to a value of 0.889% after 24 hours (Fig. 3-4 right). The porosity is slightly higher due to the dissolution of primary minerals.

Fig. 3-5: Development of pH and porosity in Carbon cap rock during acidification of brackish water solution.

The porosity of the Carbon cap rock decreases during CO₂ injection from the original 1.154% to a value of 0.152% after 24 hours (Fig. 3-5 right). The porosity is slightly lower due to the precipitation of secondary minerals.

These porosity values do not represent any significant changes and are not a risk for the stability and impermeability of cap rocks.

3.2.2 Second model step – six months of CO₂ injection into the structure

1) Reservoir rock

During the 6 months injection of CO₂ into the collector of the potential storage, there will be a stagnant trend in pH in the solution. pH is stable at the level of original equilibrated water; pH value is 5.3 (Fig. 3-6 left).

The porosity of the collector for 6 months CO₂ injection is almost unchanged (Fig. 3-6 right).

Fig. 3-6: Development of pH and porosity in solution with reservoir rock during 6 months injection of CO₂.

Any significant changes in the composition of the solution did not show during the 6 months of CO₂ injection. The proof is the slow decrease of carbonate substances in the solution (Fig. 3-7).

Fig. 3-7: Development of carbonate substances in solution with reservoir rock during 6 months injection of CO₂.

The main ions remain almost unchanged. Only Ca²⁺ decreases slowly and Mg²⁺ (Fig. 3-8A) and K⁺ grow slightly (Fig. 3-8B).

Fig. 3-8: Development of (A) Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ ions and (B) K⁺ ion in solution with reservoir rock during 6 months injection of CO₂.

These changes are caused by the dissolution of primary minerals and the precipitation of secondary mineral phases, as indicated by the mineral saturation for the Ca²⁺ ion. Dolomite, gypsum, and primary calcite are soluble, but secondary mineral phases (Canontronite, Ca-beidellit, secondary calcite) are precipitation (Fig. 3-9).

Fig. 3-9: Development of carbonate minerals saturation in acidification brackish water during the CO₂ injection.

Mg²⁺ and K⁺ grow slightly due to dolomite and K-feldspar dissolution. Albite also dissolves. Dawsonite and chalcedony precipitate (Fig. 3-10) according to the following reaction:

Fig. 3-10: Concentration development of main minerals in acidification brackish water during the CO₂ injection.

The secondary dolomite and siderite will begin to precipitate during the 6 months of CO₂ injection, if we were to consider the dissolution of the primary carbonate mineral ankerite (Fig. 3-11).

Fig. 3-11: Concentration development of main minerals in acidification brackish water during the CO₂ injection due to ankerite dissolution.

II) Paleogene cap rock

During the 6 months of CO₂ injection, there was an interaction of acidification brackish water with overlying Paleogene cap rock. There will be a stagnate pH value 5.4 (Fig. 3-12 left). pH is some lower than in original water because of achieving the hydrochemical balance between the species in solution.

The porosity of the Paleogene cap rock decreases during 6 months of CO₂ injection from the original 0.889% to a value of 0.8856% (Fig. 3-12 right). The porosity is slightly lower due to the precipitation of secondary minerals.

Fig. 3-12: Development of pH and porosity in solution with Paleogene cap rock during 6 months of CO₂ injection.

Changes in solution with Paleogene cap rock during 6 months of CO₂ injection are shown in the Figures 3-13 and 3-14. It is obvious that the carbonates are decreasing (Fig. 3-13 left). Na⁺ decreased due to Dawsonite precipitation; K⁺ increased due to K-feldspar dissolution, according to equation 6 (Fig.3-13 right).

Fig. 3-13: Development of carbonates and Na⁺, K⁺ ions in solution with Paleogene cap rock during 6 months injection of CO₂.

Ca²⁺ decreased due to Calcite precipitation; Mg²⁺ increased due to Clinocllore dissolution; SO₄²⁻ no apparent changes (Fig. 3-14):

Fig. 3-14: Development of selected components in solution with Paleogene cap rock during 6 months injection of CO₂.

Changes in mineral assemblage are illustrated on Fig. 3-15. Albite and K-feldspar dissolve, dawsonite and chalcedony precipitate (Fig. 3-15 left). Also, some calcite and siderite precipitate from the solution (Fig. 3-15 right), see equation 7 and its modification for iron ion:

Fig. 3-15: Concentration development of main minerals in solution with Paleogene cap rock during the 6 months of CO₂ injection.

III) Carbon cap rock

During the 6 months of CO₂ injection, there was an interaction of acidification brackish water with underlying Carbon cap rock. There will be a higher pH value 6.48 (Fig. 3-16 left). pH is some higher than in original water because it dissolves carbonates. The porosity of the Carbon cap rock increases during 6 months of CO₂ injection from the original 1.154% to a value of 1.284% (Fig. 3-16 right). The porosity is slightly higher due to the dissolution of primary and secondary minerals.

Fig. 3-16: pH and porosity in solution with Carbon cap rock during 6 months of CO₂ injection.

Changes in solution with Carbon cap rock during 6 months of CO₂ injection are shown in the Fig. 3-17. The concentration of carbonates in the solution increases slightly as they dissolve (Fig. 3-17 top left). Concentration of Ca²⁺ is stagnated (Fig. 3-17 top right), but concentration of Mg²⁺ increased due to Clinocllore dissolution (see equation 8), concentration of Na⁺ increased due to Dawsonite dissolution, concentration of K⁺ increased due to K-feldspar dissolution (Fig. 3-17 down left) and SO₄²⁻ ion decreased (Fig. 3-17 down right) because gypsum is dissolved.

Fig. 3-17: Development of selected components in solution with Carbon cap rock during 6 months injection of CO₂.

Changes in mineral assemblage are shown on Fig. 3-18. Albite and K-feldspar dissolve, kaolinite precipitate (Fig. 3-18 left). Also, some calcite and siderite precipitate and gypsum dissolves from the solution (Fig. 3-18 right).

Fig. 3-18: Concentration development of main minerals in solution with Carbon cap rock during the 6 months of CO₂ injection.

3.2.3 The third model for the degassing processes in reservoir and cap rocks during 500 years after CO₂ injection

The degassing process represents the time after the end of CO₂ injection into the geological structure and the relaxation period until the original partial pressure of CO₂ is restored in the structure. Water in this model is degassed to fugacity $f_{CO_2} = 0.5$ bar and cooled to 20°C, after 500 years. The model is calculated for 1 kg of water and 9000 cm³ of rock.

1) Reservoir rock

Developments of pH and porosity in solution with reservoir rock during 500 years after CO₂ injection are shown at Fig. 3-19.

Fig. 3-19: pH and porosity in solution with reservoir rock during 500 years after CO₂ injection.

It is clear from the figure that pH increased due to degassing (Fig. 3-19 left). The initial increase in pH to a value of 6.27 was a jump. Subsequently, the pH gradually increased to a value of 6.4, which was reached 500 years after the end of CO₂ injection. Porosity is

slightly higher due to the changes of mineral composition. From the initial value of 6.8%, it increased to a value of 7.5% after 500 years (Fig. 3-19 right).

Changes in the solution are best seen in the development of the HCO₃⁻ ion concentration (Fig. 3-20). Carbonates decreased in brackish water solution with reservoir rock to the value 2940 mg/l after 500 years from the end of CO₂ injection.

Fig. 3-20: Development of carbonates concentration in solution with reservoir rock during 500 years after CO₂ injection.

Other changes in the composition of the solution were mainly manifested by an increase in alkali concentrations (Fig. 3-21 left) and a decrease in Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ concentrations. Concentration of SO₄²⁻ ions stagnate (Fig. 3-21 right).

Fig. 3-21: Development of selected components in solution with reservoir rock during 500 years after CO₂ injection.

Changes in mineral composition are presented in Fig. 3-22. Albite, K-feldspar and Chlorites dissolve, Muscovite and Kaolinite precipitate (Fig. 3-22 left). Dolomite and Siderite precipitate (Figure 23 right). Chalcedony precipitate (Fig. 3-22 right). Most of Chalcedony is released from the solution, not from dissolving minerals during degassing.

Fig. 3-22: Concentration development of main minerals in solution with reservoir rock during 500 years after CO₂ injection.

Magnesite and Dawsonite also precipitated from the solution (Fig. 3-23) based on their saturation index values.

Fig. 3-23: Some minerals precipitate in solution with reservoir rock during 500 years after CO₂ injection.

II) Paleogene cap rock

Developments of pH and porosity in solution with Paleogene cap rock during 500 years after CO₂ injection are shown at Fig. 3-24.

Fig. 3-24: pH and porosity in solution with Carbon cap rock during 500 years after CO₂ injection.

pH increased due to degassing (Fig. 3-24 left) to a value of 6.32. The increase was gradual over the course of the entire 500 years.

Porosity is lower due to the precipitation of secondary mineral. From the initial value of 0.886%, it decreased to a value of 0.882% after 500 years (Fig. 3-24 right).

Changes in the concentrations of individual chemical substances in the solution are described below. Concentrations of carbonates decrease significantly (Fig. 3-25 left). Carbonates decreased in brackish water solution with Paleogene cap rock to the value 6250 mg/l after 500 years from the end of CO₂ injection (Fig. 3-25 left).

Fig. 3-25: Concentration developments of carbonates (left) and of other chemical components (right) in solution with Paleogene cap rock during 500 years after CO₂ injection.

Other changes in the composition of the solution were mainly manifested by an increase in alkali (Fig. 3-26 left) and Mg²⁺ and a decrease in Ca²⁺ (Fig. 3-26 right) concentrations. Concentration of SO₄²⁻ ions grow slightly (Fig. 3-26 right). These trends are also confirmed by changes in the mineral composition of the modelled Paleogene cap rock sample.

Fig. 3-26: Development of selected components in solution with Paleogene cap rock during 500 years after CO₂ injection.

Changes in mineral composition are presented in Fig. 3-27. K-feldspar, Albite, Muscovite and Chlorite dissolve. Chalcedony, Dawsonite and K-zeolite precipitate (Fig. 3-27 left). The images show also that secondary calcite precipitates and siderite also begins to precipitate at the end of the modelled period (Fig. 3-27 right).

Fig. 3-27: Concentration development of main minerals in solution with Paleogene cap rock during 500 years after CO₂ injection.

The initial rapid increase in the concentration of Mg²⁺ in the solution (Fig. 3-26 right) slowed down at the end of the monitored period. This is due to the dissolution of dolomite over a period of 450 years after the end of CO₂ injection. Solution conditions will change at the end of the modelled time, and this will allow the precipitation of secondary dolomite and magnesite (Fig. 3-28).

Fig. 3-28: Some Mg minerals precipitate in solution with Paleogene cap rock during 500 years after CO₂ injection.

III) Carbon cap rock

Developments of pH and porosity in solution with Carbon cap rock during 500 years after CO₂ injection are shown at Fig. 3-29.

pH increased due to degassing (Fig. 3-29 left) to a value of 6.20. The increase was gradual over the course of the entire 500 years.

Porosity is slightly higher due to the changes of mineral composition. From the initial value of 1.158%, it increased to a value of 1.162% after 500 years (Fig. 3-29 right). Porosity began to decrease again at the end of the model time.

Fig. 3-29: Development of pH and porosity in solution with Carbon cap rock during 500 years after CO₂ injection.

Changes of chemical substances concentration in the solution are shown on Fig. 3-30. Carbonates decreased in brackish water solution with reservoir rock to the value 8100 mg/l after 500 years from the end of CO₂ injection (Fig. 3-30 left). Other changes in the composition of the solution are the same as the Paleogene cap rock sample. They are represented by growth of alkalis and Mg²⁺ concentrations and a decrease in Ca²⁺ concentrations (Fig. 3-30 right). Concentration of SO₄²⁻ ions grow slightly (Fig. 3-30 right) – some increase from 525 to 541 mg/l.

Fig. 3-30: Development of selected components in solution with Carbon cap rock during 500 years after CO₂ injection.

Changes in mineral assemblage are as follows: K-feldspar, Albite, Muscovite, and Chlorite dissolve. Chalcedony, Dawsonite (Fig. 3-31 left) and Magnesite precipitate (Fig. 3-31 right). Also, that secondary calcite precipitates (Fig. 3-31 right).

Fig. 3-31: Concentration development of main minerals in solution with Carbon cap rock during 500 years after CO₂ injection.

3.3. Experiments in react chamber

Experiments in the reaction chamber realized on VSB – Technical University of Ostrava were done in two phases. The first experiments were carried out with samples of reservoir rock, the second stage of experiments was done with samples of Paleogene and Carbon cap rocks.

3.3.1 Experiments with reservoir rock samples

First experiment in the reaction chamber was carried out in 2022 at VSB – Technical University of Ostrava (Fig. 3-32). Experiments start at 10 January 2022.

Two rocks were used for a planned study of reactions with brine. Collector rocks from the deposit were used as samples for the reaction chamber. Depositional environment was described as carbonate bank. It was Vranovice dolomite. The characteristics of the samples are given in the Tabs. 2-1 and 2-4.

Four cells in reaction chamber were used for these experiments. Rock samples ZA4A were placed in the cells. Experiment in these cells will take 1, 3, 4 and 6 months.

Samples in cells of reaction chamber were flooded with bearing water. Pressure and temperature for a process were 15 MPa and 53°C. They are an assumed injection pressure in oil bearing deposit and expected temperature in the deposit.

Fig. 3-32: Two reaction chambers with four cells (left) and one cell with rock samples and brine (right).

Collector water came from a well ZA4A. Water had a brine character. Chemical type was sodium-chloride and was very strongly mineralized. The input water analysis came from the MND laboratories like cumulative sample (Tab. 3-1).

Further analyses were done in the VSB laboratory. These were water samples taken after 1, 3, 4 and 6 months of experiments. Hydrochemical classification is sodium-chloride type. Genetic classification is marine and deep buried waters. Long-term interaction with injected CO₂ will not change the brine character of the mine waters. The results are displayed in Tab. 3-2.

Tab. 3-2: Chemical analyses of water samples after experiments with reservoir rock

parameter	pH	ρ	Cond.	SO ₄	Cl	HCO ₃	NH ₄	K	Mg	Na	Ca	Li	Sr	Mn	Fe	B	
units		g/cm ³	mS/cm	[mg/l]													
Input – MND	7,1	1,0	36,5	535,0	12300,0	2580,0	32,6	252,0	107,0	8570	111,0	3,2	19,2	0,0	0,4	-	
Borehole	Month																
ZA4A	1	6,7	1,0	36,9	640,0	13250,6	2702,3	9,1	257,0	99,6	4570	285,0	2,8	17,0	0,9	0,01	45,8
	3	6,9	1,0	35,3	660,0	12727,6	3440,4	15,8	256,0	100,0	6260	315,0	2,9	13,6	1,1	94,9	43,0
	3A	7,3	1,0	34,8	630,0	13294,9	3050,0	17,5	295,0	99,3	5530	416,0	2,9	14,6	1,3	130	43,4
	4	7,2	1,0	37,2	550,0	13046,7	3225,7	19,4	463,0	94,8	8750	348,0	2,8	16,3	0,7	18,9	40,8
	6	6,8	1,0	38,0	540,0	12444,0	3660,0	19,1	334,0	92,7	6770	702,0	2,7	13,4	0,4	60,8	41,6

Development of the composition of the input brine after interaction with rock and CO₂ saturation are summarized in Tab. 3-3.

Tab. 3-3: Development of water samples composition

parameter	pH	p at 15 °C	conductivity	SO ₄ -2	Cl-	HCO ₃ -	NH ₄ ⁺	K	Mg	Na	Ca	Li	Sr	Mn	Fe
units	[-]	[g/cm ³]	[mS/cm]	[mg/l]											
MND analysis	7.0715	1,017	36,5	535	12300	2580	32,6	252	107,0	8570	111	3,17	19,2	0,01	0,35
1st month analysis	6.716	1,016	36,9	640	13251	2702	9,1	257	99,6	4570	285	2,75	17	0,88	0,01
3rd months analysis	6.896	1,016	35,3	660	12728	3440	15,8	256	99,3	6260	315	2,88	13,6	1,08	95
4th months analysis	7.220	1,016	37,2	550	13047	3226	19,4	463	94,8	8750	348	2,78	16,3	0,731	18,9
6th months analysis	6.813	1,018	38,0	540	12444	3660	19,1	334	92,7	6770	702	2,72	13,4	0,421	60,8

legend:
 decrease values
 increase values
 fluctuating values
 X stagnant values

Increase values of calcium and bicarbonate ions in brine during the experiments in react chamber indicate dissolution and transformation of original rock. Decrease or fluctuating values of sodium, magnesium, strontium, potassium, manganese, iron, and lithium represent the precipitation of secondary phases.

The used rock samples were subjected to XRD analysis at the specialized workplace of the Department of Geological Engineering at VSB – Technical University of Ostrava. XRD analysis of rock samples during the experiments in react chamber show:

- precipitation of calcite and dissolution of primary dolomite during the first month;
- formation of other secondary phases – kaolinite, muscovite, feldspar (albite, microcline and orthoclase);
- iron-dolomite and chlorite are formed at the end of the experiments.

The results are summarized in Tab. 3-4.

Tab. 3-4: Mineralogical composition of the studied reservoir rock samples (wt%)

Borehole	Month	Dol	Dol Ca-Fe	Q	Calc	Mu	Ka	Mic	Alb	Chl	Pyr
		(wt%)	(wt%)	(wt%)	(wt%)	(wt%)	(wt%)	(wt%)	(wt%)	(wt%)	(wt%)
ZA4A	0	55,04	17,95	4,01	0	2,88	3,12	7,66	7,92	1,42	
	1	36,33	27,12	7,71	7,42	2,9	4,32	6,04	8,21	0	
	3	42,43	21,32	5,78	8,66	3,38	1,43	7,15	10,03	0	
	4	63,62	11,84	2,93	1,87	4,01	2,27	8,19	5,33	0	
	6	36,45	26,39	4,49	6,49	1,79	4,13	9,75	9,74	1,69	

* Q—quartz, Mu—muscovite, Mi—microcline, Ka—kaolinite, Chl—chlorite, Calc—calcite, Dol—dolomite, Alb—albite, Pyr—Pyrite.

The formation of secondary phases reduces the porosity of the primary rock and thus its permeability. This contributes to the stability of the rock environment.

3.3.2. Experiments with cap rock samples

The second experiment in the reaction chambers was started at the end of 2022. The solid samples come from the underlying impermeable Carbon rocks (sample UH16), respectively overlying impermeable Paleogene rocks (sample ZA4).

Used water solution was the same as in the first case. Collector water came from a well ZA4A. Water had a brine character. Chemical type was sodium-chloride and was very strongly mineralized. The input water analysis came from the MND laboratories like

cumulative sample (Tab. 3-1). Further analyses were done in the VSB – Technical University of Ostrava laboratory. These were water samples taken after 1, 3, 4 and 6 months of experiments. The results are displayed in Tab. 3-5.

Tab. 3-5: Chemical analyses of water samples after experiments with cap rocks

parameter		pH	ρ	Cond.	SO ₄	Cl	HCO ₃	NH ₄	K	Mg	Na	Ca	Li	Sr	Mn	Fe	B
units			g/cm ³	mS/cm	[mg/l]												
Input	– MND	7,1	1,0	36,5	535,0	12300,0	2580,0	32,6	252,0	107,0	8570	111,0	3,2	19,2	0,0	0,4	-
Borehole	Month																
ZA4	1	7,1	1,0	37,3	380,0	25455,3	2840,2	10,8	279,0	103,0	8740	250,0	2,9	15,2	0,2	3,5	47,8
	3	7,7	1,0	37,9	500,0	13188,5	2852,4	2,7	229,0	87,2	8100	253,0	2,8	18,5	0,7	25,0	47,4
	4	6,9	1,0	35,4	550,0	12266,7	2976,8	14,8	289,0	95,2	5680	274,0		0,1	0,7	40,5	38,8
	6	6,8	1,0	35,6	600,0	11664,0	3042,7	14,7	215,0	93,6	5380	266,0		0,1	0,4	23,5	39,6
UH16	1	7,1	1,0	37,1	520,0	13224,0	2723,0	12,4	266,0	92,5	9010	161,0	2,9	14,5	0,4	5,7	48,4
	3	7,7	1,0	38,0	510,0	15705,7	3045,1	4,8	253,0	92,2	8210	293,0	2,8	19,3	0,5	3,4	49,6
	4	6,9	1,0	35,2	490,0	13294,9	3189,1	0,3	306,0	102,0	5470	349,0		0,2	0,7	39,1	39,6
	6	6,9	1,0	35,4	420,0	12763,1	3006,1	0,4	364,0	81,8	4860	195,0		0,4	0,9	40,2	37,8

Pressure and temperature for a process are 15 MPa and 53°C again. The characteristics of the samples are given in the Tabs. 2-2 and 2-4.

Four cells in reaction chamber were used for these experiments. Rock samples ZA4 and UH16 were placed in the cells. Experiment in these cells will take 1, 3, 4 and 6 months.

Increase values of calcium and bicarbonate ions in brine during the experiments in react chamber indicate dissolution and transformation of original rock. Decrease or fluctuating values of sodium, magnesium, strontium, potassium, manganese, iron, and lithium represent the precipitation of secondary phases.

The used rock samples were subjected to XRD analysis at the specialized workplace of the Department of Geological Engineering at VSB - Technical University of Ostrava. XRD analysis of rock samples during the experiments in react chamber show:

- precipitation of secondary calcite in sample of Carbon cap rock and dissolution of primary iron-dolomite and calcite in sample of Paleogene cap rock during the first month; secondary iron-dolomite is precipitated at the end of the experiment in sample of Paleogene cap rock;
- formation of other secondary phases – muscovite, feldspar (albite, microcline and orthoclase) and chlorite;
- quartz and pyrite are formed throughout the experiment with sample of Paleogene cap rock; in contrast, quartz dissolves during the experiment with the Carbon cap rock sample.

The results are summarized in Tab. 3-6.

Tab. 3-6: Mineralogical composition of the studied cap rocks samples (wt%)

Borehole	Month	Dol	Dol Ca-Fe	Q	Calc	Mu	Ka	Mic	Alb	Chl	Pyr
		(wt%)	(wt%)	(wt%)	(wt%)	(wt%)	(wt%)	(wt%)	(wt%)	(wt%)	(wt%)
ZA4	0	18,10		57,10	0,30	4,00		16,68	1,18	1,14	1,50
	1	4,31		64,85		8,35		17,12	1,22	2,11	2,04
	3	11,39		59,65		10,19		14,05	1,31	1,16	2,28
	4	12,55		56,32		7,80		17,49	1,31	2,23	2,29
	6	5,31		60,68		9,85		17,41	1,40	3,12	2,23
UH16	0			51,32	1,65	3,58		17,52	18,4	7,53	
	1			46,29	3,17	7,77		17,05	18,47	7,26	
	3			48,83		7,83		14,86	19,53	8,96	
	4			43,21	3,26	9,12		16,00	17,56	10,84	
	6			45,56		7,11		17,27	20,49	9,44	

* Q—quartz, Mu—muscovite, Mi—microcline, Ka—kaolinite, Chl—chlorite, Calc—calcite, Dol—dolomite, Alb—albite, Pyr -Pyrite.

The formation of secondary phases reduces the porosity of the primary rock and thus its permeability. This contributes to the stability of the rock environment. These results will be discussed and supplemented with the results of geochemical models.

4 CONCLUSION

The conclusions of this study are based on experiments carried out in the reaction chamber and models calculated in The Geochemist's Workbench (GWB) program.

Interactions were studied in the CO₂-rock-brackish water system, for reservoir rock and Paleogene and Carbone cap rock. The aim was to characterize the influence of CO₂ in the geological structure on mineralogical rock changes from the potential storage site.

For all rock samples, the most important chemical processes are the dissolution of carbonates (calcite and dolomite) and microcline due to acidification of the brackish water during the injection of CO₂ into the structure. The dissolution of some mineral phases during the injection and the increase in porosity in the structure affect the sequestration capacity of the reservoir rock of the potential storage site. The dissolution of carbonates and microcline was also confirmed in their study by Wang et al. (2019). Gaus et al. (2008) describes the importance of the dissolution of mineral phases for the increased storage capacity of the reservoir rock. The results of the presented study are in agreement with the conclusions of these authors. Other chemical processes that the models describe include the precipitation of magnesite, which replaces dissolving dolomite completely, and the formation of secondary carbonates as a result of the increasing pH of the brackish water in the structure over a longer period of time after injection is ceased. Carbonate minerals bind CO₂ to their structure and help to stabilize the pH of the brackish water after injecting. The consequence of this process is, however, the reduction in the porosity of the reservoir rock. Klunk et al. (2020) also observed the precipitation of magnesite in his work at elevated pressure-temperature and high salinity. In the long term, these processes are desirable. The formation of secondary phases is considered useful during the relaxation period of the deposit after CO₂ injection (Gaus 2010; Ajayi et al. 2019).

The newly formed phases close the injected CO₂ in the structure and thus contribute to the stability of the environment. They also represent a barrier for possible CO₂ leaks into the caprock (Foroutan et al. 2021; Wang et al. 2019).

The porosity of reservoir rock decreases by 1.1% during the first model period, i.e., during 6 months of injecting the porosity stagnates and after 500 years of structure relaxation the porosity increases by 0.6%. The original value of the reservoir rock porosity was 8% and the final value after the 500 relaxation years was 7.586%.

The model evolution of porosity in cap rocks is as follows:

1) The porosity of Paleogene cap rock slightly increases during the first model period (acidification of brackish water). The porosity of Paleogene cap rock during the second model step slowly decreases and after 500 years of structure relaxation the porosity decreases to the original value 0.882%.

2) The porosity of Carbon cap rock slightly decreases during the first model period (acidification of brackish water). The porosity of Carbon cap rock during the second model step slowly increases and after 500 years of structure relaxation the porosity increases to the value 1.162%.

Experiments with rock samples in the reaction chamber also confirmed similar results.

Immediately after its injection, CO₂ spreads in its supercritical form and partially dissolves into the groundwater. This process significantly changes mineralogical, hydrogeological, and geochemical conditions at the storage site. It acidifies the original groundwater of the brackish water type; it can influence hydrogeological parameters, especially the porosity and permeability of the deposit rock; it changes the mineralogical composition of the deposit rock and can mineralogically affect the confining layers in the overburden. All these reactions can be a potential risk for the CO₂ storage process in the selected structure. It is therefore necessary to understand the mechanism of these reactions and to quantify and evaluate them to ensure the safety and sustainability of storage.

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